

Human Rights and Technology

Jai Shanker Prasad Srivastava

Professor & Dean, Faculty of Legal Studies,
Motherhood University, Roorkee , Uttarakhand.

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Abstract

This article examines the use of technology in regards to human rights which are given universally to people around the globe irrespective of discrimination on any ground. The pros and cons in recent time: of newly and latest introduced artificial intelligence in preserving human rights. It also let us know the origin of human rights (i.e. from Cyrus the Great) and afterwards by the young lawyer of that time proclaimed the human right to be equal for all around the globe. The technology in today's world and its evolution and its role in development of societies and the threats which can be seen by malicious use of technology and the steps which can be taken for prevention the misuse of technology. It also explains the role of industrialization 4.0 which is the latest development and plays a vital role in various fields in different aspects. The landmark judgments by honorable courts and also mentioned the idea for resolving the following disputes arising from technologies in modern era related to the human rights.

Key words: Human Rights, Technology, Artificial Intelligence, Surveillance, Social Media.

INTRODUCTION

The impact of technology on the perception of Human Right is profound. The new digital technology widespread poses both opportunities as well as the challenges such as PRIVACY, DATA PROTECTION and FREEDOM OF OPINION AND EXPRESSION, including FREEDOM OF ASSEMBLY and ASSOCIATION. The same rights people have offline must also be protected online. As societies are developing overtime and becoming more dependent on technologies, the protection of Human Rights becomes more critical. The technology leads to the transformation in the way of exercising the rights and freedom. Increased use of digital technologies and Artificial Intelligence is continuously raising the question related to the protection of privacy. While Artificial Intelligence having huge untapped potential, unregulated Artificial Intelligence design and use is creating wide shared concerns over the violations of human rights, especially in terms of discrimination for certain segments of society as a result of "bias algorithms". "The use of technology in each of these contexts poses risks not only to rights. Rather, it also poses risks to accountability. The use of new technologies obscures and mitigates responsibility for these rights violations in ways that undermine traditional mechanisms for holding accountable those whose activities undermine respect for human rights."¹ It is important to build bridges between digital human rights organizations and civil society actors, as this has a negative impact on those who are already profiled, targeted, and harassed in the non-digital world.

By technology we mean, in the broadest sense, "any technique, process, or object that enables humans to do or make something. Technologies consist of a network of material and social components and require various forms of knowledge and human input to function properly. We argue that responding to the impact of new technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), spyware, and the digital state requires a fundamental shift in how we approach technology and private action."² "Recent research shows that addressing these impacts requires positive efforts to ensure that human rights are respected and promoted in the development and implementation of new technologies.

Moreover, traditional distinctions between public and private need to be updated to remain relevant in light of the close intertwining of government and corporate action in the context of technological innovation.³ However, the Concomitant threats became visible during COVID -19 as the use of advanced digital technologies progressed.

HUMAN RIGHTS

• HISTORY

We come from a time when there were no human rights and when people only believed that if you belonged to the right group you were safe, if not you were not cheap. But then a man named Cyrus the Great decided to change all that after winning a battle. He did something completely revolutionary and proclaimed that all slaves were free, also said that people were free to choose their religion no matter what group they belonged to and documented his words on a clay tablet as a guarantee of freedom and human rights were born, and the ideas quickly spread to Greece, Rome, and India. They noted that people by nature followed certain laws, even if they were not commanded to do so - they called this natural law, but it was repeatedly trampled on by those in power. After some time, revolutions occurred around the world and human rights were recognized. Then some other countries were conquered and appropriated by the great European empires. Then, in 1915, Indian lawyer Mahatma Gandhi organized protests and declared that all people have rights, not just those in Europe.⁴ After two world wars, the nations came together and established the United Nations (UN), whose goal was to reaffirm faith in fundamental human rights, dignity, and worth of the human person. All people are born free and equal in both dignity and rights. These words represent the reality, the goal, and the difficulty. Truth because I really believe that we are born free and equal, and Vision because we have a long way to go until we realize that truth in our world. Human rights are the essential liberties and safeguards that each and every one of us is entitled to, regardless of caste, sex, religion, belief, or race. Treating everyone equally and allowing for individual decision-making are central to the concept of rights. They are about justice, equality and freedom. All these rights are granted only on the basis of the very fact that you're a human being and your life is your life and it cannot be taken unjustly just because some people do not like you.⁵

• FOUNDATIONAL PRINCIPLES

Summing up the essence of Human Rights machinery with the following fundamental Principles:

- a) Human Rights engage all the experiences lived and the aspects of our lives, for sure it's about freedom of speech, privacy but it's also about other socioeconomic wellbeing, basic issues of social security, shelter and healthcare.
- b) Some of the rights are absolute in nature that one can never be enslaved, for instance nevertheless most rights are subject to the limitations in the public good and also essential if we're to have societies and communities.
- c) The Modern days Human Rights system is the one which imposes duties and the responsibilities on states and give right to the people to move to court if any of their right is abrogated or infringed.
- d) Most Important among all is that these basic principles are unique and there is nothing like this as it is the only roadmap or language to show the way to honor human dignity, human values in our societies as these are shared universally.⁶

Human rights unites together all for better society but then also the future is at stake and will remain at stake, if we will not remove quickly and smartly. I stated that the future is at stake because of the most recent circumstances or the problems taken place around the globe like COVID 19, Russia-Ukrain War, Climate crisis, Conflict between Israeli- Palestinian.

Rampant crisis of disinformation across our societies his driving debate with terrible consequences for all institutions. We have shocking levels of the inequalities as the poor are becoming even poorer and the rich getting ever more distant from the very poor.

To some extent Human rights are missing in action. We do not see them at center of the responses to fix our societies and to advance them.⁷

We need to do is: - *wake up, rise up, act up. and join up.*

- **TECHNOLOGIES**

The technologies have been developed over decades and were started from the Stone Age and now have come to the most recent development of the Artificial Intelligence. Artificial Intelligence is highly used technology around the globe and is capable of thinking and answering every question asked by a person. But as we all are aware of the fact that the technology is good but also have the negative impacts with the positive impacts in our societies. Technologies were invented or can say that are being developed to make the burden or working of the society in effective and easy way and same also leads to the developments in all the sectors like corporate, education, Industrialization etc.⁸

As today we are already reliant on machines for most of the work in our day to day life.

- **ACCOUNTABILITY**

“The second framework for thinking about the relationship between technology and human rights is to consider the impact that technology has on our ability to hold those responsible for rights violations accountable. Technology is not just used in good or bad ways. Rather, in many contexts, it actually works against disclosure and accountability. The use of technology can obscure and fragment authority, invalidating the mechanisms that human rights defenders and civil society organizations use to promote accountability”.⁹

Technology “makes it much harder to hold those responsible accountable because it obscures the identity of the violator. Activities achieved through automation, for example, may seem inevitable—even if they are the result of decisions that reflect and embody value judgments.”¹⁰ Technology also makes violations themselves more invisible, naturalizing activities that might otherwise be viewed as positive harm.¹¹

- **CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES**

“This section addresses three developments in technology and human rights that have become increasingly urgent in recent years: state surveillance and harassment, the role of Artificial Intelligence in automated decision making and deep fakes, and the rise of the digital state.”¹²

- **RE-CONCEIVING POWER AND LAND**

“The threat that technologies pose to human rights today is not machines that are beyond human control, as portrayed in popular culture and science fiction.”¹³ Rather, the threat is that they “centralize knowledge and power in the hands of those who already have it, and further disempowered those who do not”. We propose two concrete strategies to address these threats. One is based on the practice of technology development, the other on law.

- **ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (A.I.)**

“It is the first intelligent machine in the last invention that the machine is docile enough to tell us how to keep it under control.” Since we are reliant on machine and we use simple forms of artificial intelligence and a daily basis from Netflix, prime, to Siri, videogames, Google. “Artificial Intelligence technology is like driverless cars, autonomous drones and robots that can play games are proliferating now. This is both a little bit scary but also truly exciting because I believe artificial intelligence could give us a chance to finally find global solutions related to challenges we face we face around the globe.”¹⁴ One of the challenges we mostly face around globe is related to human right and it is also the most debatable topic around the globe.

- **IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY ON HUMAN RIGHTS**

Recently deployed artificial intelligence and other modern technologies are seen as a better way to make people aware of their human rights. This can lead to the growth of our societies, but on

the other hand, it can also be observed that this leads to inequalities and many other negative effects.¹⁵

For Instance- Artificial Intelligence can also cause real harm, as we can see overseas that artificial intelligence has lead to unfairness. Algorithms that give woman lower credit ratings, facial recognitions that discriminate people on the basis of skin color and even decided that how likely you are to be a criminal in future on the basis of skin color. Examples closer to home are as most of the important decisions by government and corporations are taken using the artificial intelligence that affects the people around.

Artificial Intelligence should give us what we want and need, not what we fear. It should always be fair and accountable in all aspects and there should be no biasness or discrimination.¹⁶

Although Artificial Intelligence can be improved in a way that it will not spread the biasness or other negative impacts in society. Then it can also be used in decision making and the decisions taken must be understandable as to prudent man.

The use of technology can also be beneficial in different aspect in respect to the government, people and corporations as well. It may leads to growth in a positive way as: - It leads to the participation in decision making and the government may also be able to acknowledge the suggestions of policies and laws made by them for governance or related to any other field as well. It will lead to the transparency and will also spread awareness widely, as most of the people are using technologies in daily routine.

For Instance: - A bill was introduced recently in respect to relocation of certain animals (like-dogs, cat, buffaloes and cows) and same was posted on internet and was mentioned that public can oppose or give views within 10 days. It was opposed by many animal lovers and public and the same effected to the revocation of the bill and were taken back.

The use of technology has been increased after the pandemic COVID 19, as during such time all the rules, regulation, policies and orders passed were published electronically (i.e. technology) and same made things more resilient but with the same benefit their arises a need to make strict policies related to securing the privacy offline as well as online, so that the data and other information are not used illegally and must make sure that no person is discriminated virtually or in real world.

Technologies also play a vital role in decision making in corporations and industries, also it may be proved as a source of decision making in law enforcement agencies and justice delivering in future.

Government at national lever and United Nations at the International level must endeavor to restrict the malicious and illegal use of technologies all over the globe and also take some preventive measures as from online & offline harassment and surveillance (more than required). For the same can decide the collective sanction for prevention and protection of Human Rights.

For Instance: - Some people after surveillance the people around, who are endeavoring for the protection, enforcement and spreading awareness about the human rights and through surveillance are finding their location and assassinating them (i.e. misuse of technology).

• OBSERVATION OF SUPREME CORT OF INDIA

In D.K. Basu v. State of West Bengal ¹⁷The Supreme Cort has been observed that “the larger objective of developing systems to make arrests more transparent and the authorities more responsible for rights abuses was also given a lot of attention. The Court even advised putting in place a system of adequate apparatus for documenting and notifying all arrests and detentions in real-time. Finally, the Court published a set of requirements/guidelines to be followed in all situations of arrests and detentions as preventative measures, in order to address the legal void in this area. The Court gave several directives, including, the commission of oversight bodies at different levels of governance, mandatory installation of CCTV cameras at prisons and the availability of its footage to the victim’s family, police stations and investigative agencies, and conduction of medical examination of the arrested post-arrest, among others.”¹⁸

In “Hussainara Khatoon & Ors. v. Home Secretary, State of Bihar & Ors.”¹⁹ The Supreme Court, alarmed by the criminal justice system’s long-term imprisonment of indigent defendants, ruled that bail processes in India must meet the *Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India* (1978) criteria of being ‘reasonable, just, and fair’.²⁰ A method that put so many individuals in prison without trial for so long could not be considered reasonable, just, or fair, as required by Article 21. “The Court emphasized the importance of changing the law’s approach to pretrial detention and ensuring a “reasonable, just, and fair” system. It fought for comprehensive bail reforms to make a pretrial release from jail accessible to the wealthy and the poor equally.”²¹

The Court advocated for the implementation of fresh measures to ensure that under trials do not run from justice without placing an inequitable burden on impoverished under trials after recognizing the “property focused strategy” as an unjust obstacle to getting released from jail. “One of these was the ‘roots in the community’ approach, which stated that someone with roots in the community who is unlikely to flee might be freed on a personal bond. It also established criteria for determining an accused’s eligibility for release under this technique. After a thorough investigation, if the court determines that the accused has links to the community and that there is no significant danger of non-appearance, the accused may be freed on a personal bond. Even when giving personal bail, the bond value should not be based just on the nature/severity of the accusation against the accused, but rather on their financial situation and the likelihood of absconding.”²² “Therefore, the Court decided that the criterion of financial stability of the accused should not result in the denial of bail and suspension of personal liberty to impoverished and indigent people under Article 21 of the Indian Constitution.”²³

“*People’s Union for Civil Liberties v. Union of India*”²⁴ “According to the ruling of the Supreme Court in several cases over time, the ‘right to privacy’ has been upheld as a fundamental right and treated as a part of the ‘right to life and personal liberty’ under Article 21 of the Indian Constitution. When it came to phone interceptions, the Court decided that this right includes the ability to have a private telephone conversation in the privacy of one’s home or business. The right to free expression under Article 19(1)(a) implied the ability to openly express one’s beliefs and ideas by speaking, writing, printing, photography, or any other means. When someone uses the telephone, they are expressing this right of theirs. Thus, telephone taps limited this privilege and would be unlawful unless it fell within one of the Article 19(2) reasons for limitation.”²⁵

“The Court noted that Section 5(2) permitted the Central Government or State Government, or any official particularly empowered in this regard, to intercept messages (including calls) in the case of a public emergency or for the benefit of public safety.”²⁶ “In addition, the state had to be convinced that it was essential in the interests of India’s sovereignty and integrity, security, cordial relations with other governments, public order, or the prevention of inducement to commit an offence. Before the government could authorize an interception under Section 5(2), two sets of requirements had to be met. However, it was determined that Section 5(2) did not specify a mechanism for exercising this right to intercept. Hence, the ability to wiretap telephone calls becomes arbitrary, whimsical, or coercive. This did not fulfil the ‘just, fair, and reasonable’ requirement. While the Court did not rule Section 5(2) illegal, it did establish a series of procedural protections for the use of Section 5(2)’s telephone interception power.”²⁷ “It gave directions for the establishment of a Review Committee, imposing accountability on certain office-holders, and mandating maintenance of records for phone tapping, among others.”²⁸

In “*Selvi & Ors. v. State of Karnataka & others*”²⁹ “The apex court after analyzing the methods employed in these tests and the limited trustworthiness of their results, the Court concluded that Article 20(3) prevented the accused from being forced to make incriminating remarks. Article 20(3) served as an important safeguard for the accused’s rights by prohibiting such coerced comments.”³⁰ Without it, “investigators would have a motive to force the accused to make incriminating

admissions, which would encourage the use of torture and other “third degree” tactics by the police. Article 20(3) also safeguarded Article 21’s right to personal liberty in this way.”³¹

The Supreme Court “disagreed with the High Court’s finding, holding that if these tests/methods were provided to the accused involuntarily/compulsorily, the statement or information received from them would be obtained by coercion, threat, or incentive. This would be inadmissible as evidence since it would prima facie breach Article 20(3) protection”³² against coerced self-incrimination.

Hence, the “accused had a right to remain silent in response to queries whose responses would be incriminating, and any use of force, intimidation, or coercion to compel the accused to speak would be a violation of Article 20(3). Article 20(3) prohibits coerced testimony, and since narcotics analysis involves the accused speaking up regarding his own crime, such testimony would be forbidden by Article 20(3). Polygraph examinations and the BEAP test, on the other hand, were not dependent on the accused’s spoken evidence, but rather on conclusions formed from their physiological reactions to inquiries or probes.”³³

“The Court decided that the prohibition on ‘testimonial compulsion’ in Article 20(3) did not apply just to spoken answers, but also to non-verbal responses. The physiological reactions of the accused while responding to questions were used to make conclusions in polygraph or BEAP tests. Because the replies were based on the accused’s personal information, the physiological reactions and, by extension, the results/inferences were as well. Therefore, the findings of these tests were based on the accused’s personal information.”³⁴ Since they collected more than merely physical characteristics or data for identification or confirmation, they violated Article 20(3). Stated differently, gathering an accused person’s physiological responses during a polygraph or BEAP test was not the same as getting a sample of their handwriting or fingerprints because the former required the subject to provide personal information, while the latter did not.

Regarding the fourth point, the Court decided that administering any of these tests under duress or obligation violated the subject’s “personal liberty” because it violated their right to privacy and qualified as “cruel, inhuman, and degrading treatment” under Article 21 when it came to interfering with their mental processes. Additionally, the information obtained using these methods violated the right to a fair trial. There is no compelling public interest argument that can be used to support the infringement of fundamental rights, such as the prohibition against self-incrimination.

The Court did point out that the protections provided by Article 20(3) would only apply to the forced administration of these tests. If the accused freely agreed to any of these tests, protection would not be given. In the event that the forced administration occurred during civil proceedings, the protection would not be available. The results of the tests do not constitute evidence, even if they are administered with the accused’s consent. Section 27 of the Indian Evidence Act, 1872, only allows for the admission of information or materials in court that were acquired subsequently using the test results.

Conclusion

Each and every human has worth and dignity. Understanding and upholding human rights is a means of appreciating the worth of every individual. A group of concepts relating to equity and justice make up human rights. They cherish our freedom to live our lives as we see fit and to reach our full potential as people. They are about living a life free from discrimination, fear, and harassment. A group of essential rights that people all across the world have determined are essential is known as human rights. The rights to life, a fair trial, freedom from torture and other harsh and inhumane treatment, freedom of speech, freedom of religion, and access to healthcare, education, work, and a high standard of living are among them.

These fundamental rights apply to everyone, regardless of gender, age, economic or social status, and opinions. Human rights are therefore universal and pervasive.

Everyone is entitled to these essential rights, regardless of gender, age, social or economic standing, or personal beliefs. Human rights are therefore ubiquitous and universal. Values like respect, equality, and tolerance can lessen social conflict. Human rights principles can assist us in building the society we desire. In recent decades, there has been a significant shift in the way we conceptualize and apply the ideas of human rights. This has produced a number of advantages.

Most nations' "COVID-19 preventive and mitigation actions were sudden and difficult, with the prolonged lockdown putting a burden on economic activities. Many people were affected by the misery and disruptions caused by human rights limitations and abuses, but certain marginalized communities were particularly sensitive to the pandemic's negative impacts. Children, women, minorities and the elderly have been the worst affected stakeholders during the pandemic-imposed lockdown and the ensuing restrictions on human rights. Attacks on democracy, political instability, economic sanctions, and the COVID-19 epidemic all pose significant obstacles to the current human rights situation across the world."³⁵

Despite the projected popularity that strives to deploy technology for social good. Technology can't solve the social problems. For technologies to have more transformative effect, we must be more mindful of that who is building it, for what purpose and what are the kinds of powers and privileges which are embedded within it. Thus, ensuring equitable access in respect of the technology is merely a start; but same is not enough. Technologies rather than working in a vacuum depend upon expertise network which are complex, maintenance and structural inequalities that are embodied in governance.

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